

Recognition of Pre-segmented Characters in Printed Bilingual Gujarati-English Text

Shailesh A. Chaudhari
Dept. of Information & Comm. Technology,
Veer Narmad South Gujarat, University,
Surat, India
Shailesh_mca@yahoo.com

Ravi M. Gulati
Dept. of Computer Science,
Veer Narmad South Gujarat, University,
Surat, India
rmgulati@gmail.com

Abstract ----- Character recognition is always a challenging task for OCR of multilingual documents. Most of the script identification work is done on paragraph/block, line, and word level, but no significant work is done at character level. Generally English language is interspersed with most of the regional documents in India. In this paper a system is proposed to address such a diverse situation at character level in the context of Gujarati and English language used in Gujarat state, a western part of India. Experiments are carried out on pre-segmented multi font and multi-sized characters of both Gujarati and English. In this work features are extracted using Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). The input character is identified and recognized as either English or Gujarati character. As it is a multi-class problem, multi-class SVM has been used for classification and recognition. From the experiment promising results have been reported. To assess the global recognition accuracy 10-fold cross validation is used. The average recognition rates obtained are 98.53, 89.62%, 89.57%, and 91.56% using kNN, SVM_Linear, SVM_Polynomial, and SVM_RBF classifiers respectively.

Keywords—Script; Bi-lingual; Feature Extraction; Classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Script identification is the first step of multi-lingual OCR. Today with widespread use and application of computers and multimedia technologies, there is an increasing demand to create paperless environment. Therefore all printed documents are required to convert into digital form. In the early 1990's, several document analysis systems have been developed to handle the document contains only a single language. Script identification had been given little attention, because one can assume document's script from its country of origin.

In the context of multi-lingual country like India where more than one language are used to create documents like, bus reservation form, passport application forms, competitive examination question papers, bank challan, language transaction books, etc. In such environment, first script identification is necessary for further processing of multilingual OCR.

The fundamental issue in document image analysis is script and language identification to determine the underlying

script of document text in image format. The multi-lingual documents raise many challenges like, script identification, language determination, text reading direction and differing character sets. Also most of the document images are affected by noise or printing quality or scanning resolution. This has motivated us to develop a method for script identification and character recognition in printed bilingual Gujarati-English Text.

In this paper, pre-segmented character recognition technique for printed bilingual Gujarati-English text is proposed. The proposed technique first creates a vector of energy coefficients after applying DCT to input character image. The underlying character image is then recognized by using SVM classifier with different kernel functions.

II. RELATED WORK

Script is the graphical representation of the writing system used to write statements expressed in a language. It can be referred to a particular kind of writing and the set of characters used in it. Script Identification plays key role in document image analysis especially when the environment is multi script.

Initially a global approach based attempt was made to distinguish Asian (Chinese, Japanese and Korean) and European (Roman) scripts in [12][13]. This method examines presence and location of upward concavities of characters in the text images. To separate English and Arabic language at text line level by horizontal projection was presented in [14]. In this technique, researchers observe that the horizontal projection profiles of Arabic text have one major peak with respect to the baseline, whereas, projections of English text have two major peaks with respect to baseline.

In India the major contribution for script identification work is presented by Chaudhuri and Pal in [1, 2, 3, 9]. First an attempt was made to distinguish the Roman, Bangla and Devnagari scripts at text line level. Most of the characters of both Bangla and Devnagari have a horizontal line at the top of the text (Headline). This Headline is used as the feature to separate Roman lines from the Bangla and Devnagari lines.

A morphological reconstruction based approach was proposed in [4] for script identification at word level. In this work morphological erosion and opening is used by

reconstruction of words in four directions horizontal, vertical, right, and left diagonal using line structuring elements and also the hole filling is performed for those character which contains loop.

A bilingual OCR system for printed Kannada and English is presented in [5]. Here Gabor function based features are used to identify the script at word level using pre-trained neural classifier. To separate Kannada and English characters, Wavelet descriptors are used as features with neural network for classification. A wavelet descriptors based bilingual OCR system for printed Kannada and English characters is presented in [6]. An initial work for bilingual printed Gujarati-English documents is reported in [15, 16, 17].

A statistical feature based technique for script identification is proposed in [22]. First the image is binarized and noise is removed using a Gaussian low-pass filter. Then, gray-level cooccurrence matrix is calculated. After forming gray-level co-occurrence matrix, features like energy, entropy, inertia, contrast, local homogeneity, cluster shade, cluster prominence and information measure of correlation are calculated. Finally, scripts like Bangla, Devanagari, Telugu and Roman are identified and multilayer perceptron had shown highest classification rate.

III. FEATURE EXTRACTION

In this research work DCT based energy coefficients are used as features. Discrete cosine transform was initially used for energy compaction. DCT is an orthogonal transformation that is very widely used in image and signal processing due to its strong energy compaction property. DCT, now have been of growing interest among the pattern recognition community.

DCT converts data of the image into its elementary frequency components. It operates on real data with even symmetry. It expresses data as a sum of cosine functions and normally allows a reduction in the size of data to process, because most of the visually significant information for the image is stored in just a few coefficients of DCT in the form of energy. It clusters high value coefficients in the upper left corner and low value coefficients in the bottom right of the array (m,n) where [m n] is the image size. Therefore, we can use only high value coefficients in the upper left corner for training as well as recognition purpose and ignore the low value coefficients in the bottom left corner.

The two dimensional DCT equation is defined as equation (1).

$$F(u, v) = \alpha(u)\alpha(v) \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} \sum_{y=0}^{N-1} f(x, y) \cos \left[\frac{\pi(2x+1)u}{2N} \right] \cos \left[\frac{\pi(2y+1)v}{2N} \right] \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

f (x, y) is the image intensity function and F(u, v) is a 2D matrix of DCT coefficients. Block-based implementation and the entire image are the two implementations of the DCT. A 8x8 block of DCT has been used in this research as shown in Fig.1. The DCT is applied to the whole part of the image to obtain the frequency coefficient matrix of the same size.

Fig. 12D DCT basis functions transformation (N = 8)

The basis functions for 8x8 block (N=8) are shown in figure. It can be noted that the basis functions exhibit a progressive increase in frequency both in the vertical and horizontal direction.

It is worth noting that most of the transformed coefficients have very small values and only a few coefficients have higher magnitudes. This shows the energy compaction capabilities of DCT. Low frequencies are correlated with the illumination conditions and high frequencies represent noise and small variations. To reduce the data size, some of the important coefficients are selected and remaining is discarded. This plays an important part in the feature extraction process.

Only a 10th of the coefficients have important values, which can be preserved as the feature vector of a character. There arises a need to determine the proper size for normalization and further, estimation of feature vectors for training. In our experiment, we explored normalized sizes of binarized image, 32x32. After the input image is binarized, the connected components are scaled to 32x32 size for unit normalization. A DCT based transformation for Gujarati character ‘Ka’ is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 DCT transformation of printed Gujarati Character 'Ka'

The high value coefficients are stored in the upper left corner and the low values components in the bottom right corner of the transformed matrix. So, we can ignore the low value coefficients and use only high value coefficients for the

training as well as recognition purpose. In present work, first 75 coefficients are considered and extracted in a zigzag order

and stored in a vector sequence as shown in Fig. 3

Fig. 3 Rearrangement of DCT coefficients with zigzag order

By applying various transformations, an image of a character is represented by this feature.

IV. CLASSIFICATION

The core task of classification is to use the feature vectors provided by feature extraction algorithm to classify and assign the object/pattern to a category. To perceive the behavior of proposed algorithm, a comprehensive study has been made through experimental tests that are conducted on bi-script database using SVM classifier. kNN and SVM classifiers are used for classification and recognition of printed text.

k-NN is a supervised learning algorithm used for script classification. The four features are extracted from the test image X and these feature values are compared with feature values stored in the knowledge base. The k-NN algorithm uses euclidean distance to measure the distance between the test sample and the k neighbors. After careful determination of the k nearest neighbours, a simple majority of these k-nearest neighbours is to be predicted for the query image word.

SVM is originally a binary classifier which classifies dataset by finding optimal hyper plane. It is also a supervised learning method. The power of SVM lies in its ability to transform data to a high dimensional space where the data can be separated using a hyper plane. SVM is a well-developed technique to create optimal hyper plane which distinct two classes by maximizing the distance or margin between two classes.

The SVM cannot be used directly to solve multi-class problem. In the context of multi-class problem SVM can be used with variations. They are one against one and one against all. In this research one against all is used which compares each group with a group consisting of all rest of the groups. To avoid dealing directly with the high dimensional space and excessive computations, SVM with several kernel functions are used as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. SVM KERNEL FUNCTIONS

Linear Kernel	$K(x, y) = X^T Y$
Polynomial Kernel	$K(x, y) = (X^T Y + 1)^d$
RBF Kernel	$K(x, x_i) = \exp\{-\gamma \ x - y\ ^2\}$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiments are carried out extensively for the proposed algorithm on the DCT based features for the recognition of printed Gujarati basic characters and English uppercase and lowercase characters with kNN and various kernel functions of SVM classifier. Since a standard database for Indian script recognition is not available, a dataset of 12040 characters has been prepared. The collected data set contains 4760 Gujarati

Characters, 3640 English Uppercase and 3640 English Lowercase Characters.

To obtain the recognition results, 10-fold cross validation has been used. Here one division is used for testing and remaining nine divisions for training. This has been done 10 times, each time changing the testing dataset to different division and considering remaining divisions for training. Thus 10 sets of feature vectors containing training and testing dataset in the size ratio of 9:1 has been got. Global accuracy of different datasets with kNN and various SVM kernel functions is shown in Table 2. An average percentage of recognition accuracy of 98.53, 89.62%, 89.57%, and 91.56% are achieved using kNN, SVM_Linear, SVM_Po3nomial, and SVM_RBF classifiers respectively and is presented in Fig. 4.

Table 2. 10-Fold classification results with different classifiers

Data set	knn	linear	poly	rbf
fold1	99.50	93.36	93.36	93.85
fold2	98.92	92.19	92.11	93.94
fold3	97.34	83.55	83.22	86.33
fold4	99.41	87.62	87.62	94.35
fold5	98.58	90.03	90.03	88.21
fold6	99.25	92.44	92.44	93.60
fold7	98.33	91.36	91.36	92.52
fold8	96.85	85.80	85.71	88.17
fold9	99.25	90.37	90.37	91.86
fold10	97.85	89.45	89.45	92.77
Max	99.50	93.36	93.36	94.35
Min	96.85	83.55	83.22	86.33
Avg	98.53	89.62	89.57	91.56

Fig. 4 Average Accuracy with Different Classifiers

From the Table 1, it is observed that the average recognition accuracy is very close to 100%. The important thing to notice here is that, looking at the number of classes and types of characters, the recognition accuracy is encouraging. However, an effort is on to increase the recognition accuracy for 100% by identifying and adding the dominant features to the present feature vector.

VI. CONCLUSION

A DCT based feature extraction from character image is presented for classification and character recognition at character level. As it is a unique attempt to address the issue of OCR for bilingual Gujarati - English printed text, many challenges were addressed. It is assumed that the text is in well printed form. The worst case recognition accuracy rate still needs to be improved. The reported work here is only for basic Gujarati characters and English uppercase and lowercase characters. The script identification and recognition accuracy is very promising as it is just beginning of untouched research area. The work hopefully will be further extended for hand written bilingual Gujarati - English text as well as other bilingual Indian documents.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chaudhuri.B.B and Pal.U, "An OCR system to read two Indian language scripts: Bangla and Devnagari (Hindi)", *In Proc. 4th ICDAR, Uhn*, 18-20 August, 1997.
- [2] U.Pal and B.B. Chaudhuri, "Script Line Separation from Indian Multi-Script Documents," *Proc. Int'l Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition*, pp. 406-409, Sept. 1999.
- [3] Pal U and Chaudhuri.B.B, "Automatic identification of English, Chinese, Arabic, Devnagari and Bangla script line", *Proc. 6th Intl. Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR'01)*, pages 790-794,2001.
- [4] B.V. Dhandra, P. Nagabhushan, M. Hangarge, R. Hegadi, and V.S. Malemath, "Script Identification Based on Morphological Reconstruction in Document Images," *Proc. IEEE Int'l Conf. Pattern Recognition*, vol. 2, pp. 950-953, Aug. 2006.
- [5] R Sanjeev Kunte and R D Sudhaker Samuel "A Bilingual Machine-Interface OCR for Printed Kannada and English Text Employing Wavelet Features " *10th International Conference on Information Technology*, 0-7695-3068-0/07, 2007 IEEE
- [6] B.V.Dhandra and Mallikarjun Hangarge "On Separation of English Numerals from Multilingual Document Images", *Journal of Multimedia*, VOL. 2, NO. 6, NOV. 2007
- [7] M. C. Padma and P. A. Vijaya "Global Approach for Script Identification using Wavelet Packet Based Features" *International Journal of Signal Processing, Image Processing and Pattern Recognition* Vol. 3, No. 3, September, 2010
- [8] Basavaraj Patil and N.V. Subbareddy. "Neural network based system for script identification in Indian documents", *Sadhana* Vol. 27, part-1, pp 83-97, 2002.
- [9] U. Pal, S. Sinha, and B.B. Chaudhuri, "Multi-Script Line Identification from Indian Documents," *Proc. Int'l Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition*, pp. 880-884, Aug. 2003.
- [10] Dhanya.D, Ramakrishnan.A.G And Peeta Basa Pati, "Script Identification In Printed Bilingual Documents," *Sadhana*, Vol. 27, Part-1, Pp. 73-82, 2002.
- [11] S. Chanda and U. Pal "English, Devnagari and Urdu Text Identification", *Proceedings of the International Conference on Cognition and Recognition*, pp.538-545, 2005.
- [12] Spitz.A.L, "Determination Of The Script And Language Content Of Document Images," *IEEE Tran. On Pattern Analysis And Machine Intelligence*, 1994.
- [13] Spitz.A.L, "Determination Of The Script And Language Content Of Document Images," *IEEE Tran. On Pattern Analysis And Machine Intelligence*, Vol. 19, Pp.234-245, 1997.
- [14] Elgammal.A.M and Ismail.M.A, "Techniques for Language Identification for Hybrid Arabic-English Document Images," *Proc. Sixth Int'l Conf. Document Analysis and Recognition*, pp. 1100-1104, 2001.
- [15] S. Chaudhari and R. Gulati "Script Identification from bilingual Gujarati-English Documents", *International Journal of Computer*

- Applications (IJCA)*, Vol. 93, 2014
- [16] S. Chaudhari and R. Gulati “[Script Identification Using Gabor Feature and SVM Classifier](#)”, *Elsevier Procedia Computer Science*, Vol. 79, pp. 85–92, 2016.
- [17] S. Chaudhari and R. Gulati , “A Comparative Analysis of Feature Extraction Techniques and Classifiers Inaccuracies for Bilingual Printed Documents (Gujarati-English)”, *International Journal of Applied Information Systems (JAIS)*, Vol. 1, 2016.
- [18] J. Dholakia, A. Negi, S. Rama Mohan, “Zone Identification in the Printed Gujarati Text”, *Proceedings of the 2005 Eight International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR’ 05)* 1520-5263, 2005.
- [19] Apurva A. Desai, “Gujarati handwritten numeral optical character reorganization through neural network”, *Elsvier, Pattern Recognition* 43 (2010) 2582-2589, 2010.
- [20] Apurva A. Desai, “Handwritten Gujarati numeral optical character Recognition using Hybrid Feature Extraction Technique”, *Proceedings of International Conference on Image processing, computer vision & pattern recognition, IPCV’ 10*, pp.733-739, 2010.
- [21] Nafiz. Arica and Fatos T. Yarman-Vural. An Overview of character recognition focused on off-line handwriting”, *IEEE Transactions on System, Man, Cybernetics-Part C: Applications and Reviews*. vol. 31, no. 2, 2001.
- [22] Singh PK, Dalal SK, Sarkar R, Nasipuri M ” Page-level script identification from multi-script handwritten documents”. *In:3rd international conference on computer, communication, control and information technology, Hooghly, pp 1–6. doi:10.1109/C3IT.2015.7060113*

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